

Effect of Crude Oil Exposure on Kidney of Diabetic Wistar Rats Treated with Metformin

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Abstract

Crude oil contains significant quantity of volatile organic compounds in form of monocyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and aliphatic hydrocarbons such as benzene, toluene, xylene and hexane (BTXH). Toxicological studies of their exposure to diabetic organisms has only been reported in few studies. This study was conducted to ascertain whether or not crude oil exposure affects kidney functions in diabetic rats exposed to metformin and to what extent. Diabetes was induced by intra-peritoneal injection of 65mg/kg streptozocin (STZ) dissolved in citrate buffer which was confirmed 48 h after the injection of STZ. Rats were subjected to oral treatment for four (4) weeks with 250mg/kg b.w. metformin and 200mg/kg b.w. aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* in the presence of challenging agent (crude oil). Treatment with the extract plus standard drug had maintained the electrolyte contents and lowered urea levels compared to diabetic control and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil. Creatinine level of rats treated with the extract plus standard was closely similar to that of normal control rats. Histological examination revealed normal features of kidney in control group, whereas diabetic animals treated with the aqueous extract plus standard drug exposed to crude oil had slight tubular necrosis. There was necrosis and tubular adhesion in diabetic rats exposed to crude oil, treated with standard drug only, with normal features of glomerulus in diabetic positive control rats. Therefore, crude oil exposure causes kidney dysfunction in diabetic rats treated with metformin which can be reduced with the intake of garlic.

Keywords: *Allium sativum*, Crude oil, Diabetes, Kidney dysfunction, Metformin

1.0 Introduction

Crude oil is a reservoir of various chemicals with potential toxicity [1]. Exposure to petroleum hydrocarbon has been linked with alteration of body homeostasis bringing about changes in the gross structures of organs and tissues [2]. About 24% of deaths arising from non-communicable diseases (NCDs) have been associated with exposures to environmental contaminants [3]. The growing human population and industrialization has led to the increase release of petroleum hydrocarbon into the environment [3].

Since her independence in 1960, petroleum has been the primary source of revenue in Nigeria [2]. It is an integral part of the development of modern Nigeria [2]. Multiple factors contribute to the development of NCDs in humans [5]. Besides,

exposure to chemicals, inhalation, ozone and regular traffic-related air pollutants have been reported to enhance development of NCDs [6], [7], [8]. Most of these chemicals are derived from crude oil. Frequent exposures to crude oil and petroleum hydrocarbons are not safe for healthy living [8]. Some level of toxicity may arise as a result of exposures [8]. The toxic properties may be due to one or more of the many petroleum hydrocarbon compounds of present in crude oil [4]. These compounds, when exposed could confer varied levels of toxicity to the individuals [7]. The growing interest in crude oil exploration, storage, transport therefore demands toxicity risk assessment of the various petroleum hydrocarbons [1].

Diabetes mellitus is one of the serious public health problems with increasing prevalence in individuals/communities with residential or occupational exposures to petroleum hydrocarbons [2].

Riverine region is the region where active crude oil exploration takes place with growing incidence of NCDs [3]. One of such NCDs is diabetes mellitus. It is a serious public health problem associated with high morbidity and mortality rates [8]. Use of synthetic drugs such as metformin have led to reduced morbidity and mortality burden from the disease, thus improving the quality of life of diabetic patients [9]. However, exposure to crude oil has been postulated to augment disease burden leading to organ damage and dysfunction especially the kidney but no scientific or concrete experimental evidence is reported.

The present study investigated the effect of sub-acute exposures to 5% crude oil on kidney function parameters of diabetic rats treated with metformin

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Crude Oil

Bonny Light Crude oil for the study was obtained from Ebedei Oil Terminal, Delta State, Nigeria.

2.1.2 Experimental animals

A total of thirty (30) albino rats weighing between 150-200g were purchased from the animal house, Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. They were fed normal rat chow and allowed access to clean water *ad libitum*. The rats were kept in wire mesh cages for a period of two weeks to acclimatize before the commencement of the experiment.

2.1.3 Plant Material

Allium sativum fruit was purchased from Chake market, Katsina, Katsina state Nigeria. It was identified and authenticated at herbarium of the Department of Biology, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. It was sliced into small pieces, air dried under the shade and grinded into powder using pestle and mortar and stored in sealed plastic container until required.

2.1.4 Acquisition of Metformin

Metformin was purchased from Impulse Pharma PVT. Ltd, Maharashtra State, India marketed by DON-J Pharmacy Nig. Ltd. Kano Nigeria.

2.2.0 Methods

2.2.1 Plant Material Extraction

Allium sativum was sliced in to small pieces, air dried at room temperature for five days, pulverized into powder using pestle and mortar, and then stored in sealed plastic containers until required. Exactly 200g of the powdered plant was soaked into 600 ml of distilled water for 48 h, and then filtered with Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The extract was concentrated using water bath maintained at a temperature of 40 °C, and stored at 4 °C until required.

2.2.2 Induction of Diabetes

Diabetes was induced by a single intra-peritoneal injection of 65 mg/kg streptozocin (sigma St Louis, M.O., USA) dissolved in 0.9% citrate buffer to overnight fasted rats using insulin syringe. Diabetes mellitus was confirmed after 72 hours of streptozocin administration by measuring fasting blood glucose of overnight of fasted animals (FBG). The ACCU CHECK Glucometer was used to measure the glucose with compatible strip. Rats with FBG >8.0 mmol/l were considered diabetic [9].

2.2.3 Animal grouping and experimental protocol

Group 1: Normal control rats

Group 2: untreated diabetic rats.

Group 3: diabetic rats exposed to 5 % crude oil

Group 4: diabetic rats, treated orally with metformin (250mg/kg b.w.) for four weeks.

Group 5: diabetic rats, exposed to 5% crude oil, treated with 250 mg/kg b.w of metformin by oral gavage.

Group 6: diabetic rats, exposed to 5% crude oil, treated with 200 mg/kg b.w. of garlic extract and 250 mg/kg b.w. of metformin by oral gavage.

Metformin and extract were administered to the rats by oral gavage for four weeks. Crude oil exposure was through water

2.2.4 Body weight

The body weight of all the animals before induction and within days of treatment were weekly recorded using digital weighing balance M-METLAR (QC PASS KH03).

2.2.5 Blood sample collection and clinical chemistry

After the last treatment, rats were fasted 12 hour after which they were anaesthetized by dropping individual animal in a plastic jar saturated with diethyl ether vapor. The rats were then removed from the jar and blood samples collected through cardiac puncture into labelled plastic specimen bottles containing heparin. They were then centrifuged at 4000 g for ten minutes to obtain plasma which was pipetted in to specimen test tubes for other biochemical analyses.

2.2.6 Determination of Biochemical Parameters

Plasma creatinine was determined using Jaffe's method as described by [10]. Plasma urea was determined using the Berthelot colorimetric method [11]. Electrolytes (Na^+ and K^+) were determined using flame photometry method. Plasma bicarbonate level was estimated by back titrimetric method described by [12]

2.2.7 Statistical analysis:

The data obtained were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and analyzed using SPSS version 22 software. The significance among groups was determined by One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Means regarded significant at $P < 0.05$.

3.0 Results

During administration of the extract, there was no grossly negative effect such as restlessness, convulsion, respiratory distress, coma or mortality observed/encountered. However, there was observed reduced reaction to noise, resting at the corner of cages and slow movement of rats after administration of the extract. The reduced reaction to noise suggests the depressant effect of the extract on central nervous system.

The results of the effect of treatment with aqueous extract of *A. sativum* and standard drug on body

weight changes of diabetic rats are presented in Table 1. The results indicate that streptozotocin injection resulted in drastic decrease in body weight of rats compared with that of normal control. Administration of the extract and standard drug (metformin) resulted significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in body weight of the rats compared with untreated diabetic rats and untreated diabetic rats exposed to crude oil. There was no statistically significant change in body weight of the rats treated with the extract (200mg/kg) plus standard drug (250mg/kg) compared to normal control in the first week of treatment. The same effect was observed for diabetic rats treated with standard. However, after 14 days of treatment, the body weight increase significantly ($p < 0.05$) in rats that received the extract and standard drug despite exposure to crude oil.

Table 2 presents the effect of administration of aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* and standard drug on kidney functions of diabetic rats exposed to crude oil. The results indicate that, rats treated with aqueous extract plus standard drug showed significant protection of kidneys as it significantly ($p < 0.05$) lowered/reduced the urea, maintained sodium, potassium and bicarbonate levels compared with diabetic control and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil without treatment. Compared to normal control rats however, the level of plasma electrolytes (sodium, potassium and bicarbonate), urea, and creatinine were statistically the same ($p > 0.05$) to that of normal control rats. This was supported by results from histological examination of nephritic tissue sections of control and experimental rats treated with 200mg/kg and 250mg/kg of aqueous extract and standard drug respectively, exposed to crude oil (Plate 1a-f).

From the plates (1a-f), normal control rats showed normal features of kidney, whereas diabetic rats treated with the aqueous extract plus standard drug exposed to crude oil had slight tubular necrosis. There was tubular adhesion and necrosis of kidney tubule in the rats that received standard drug only but exposed to crude oil. There was found normal features of glomerulus and tubular cells in diabetic positive control rats.

Table 1: Change in body weight of rats between week one and week four of treatment with aqueous extract of *A. sativum* and standard drug.

Group	Initial	Weekly Weight (g)			
		1	2	3	4
A	132.4±20.42	148.2±11.69 ^b	169.6±16.13 ^a	196.0±13.29 ^a	205.6±14.30 ^a
B	120.8±33.2	147.7±40.63 ^b	125.1±57.9 ^c	108.1±61.1 ^d	105.4±81.07 ^c
C	134.2±20.86	174.1±31.18 ^a	147.6±27.21 ^b	136.8±30.13 ^c	126.8±32.98 ^b
D	124.0±29.31	146.4±25.71 ^b	124.8±20.58 ^c	130.9±16.0 ^c	126.8±16.20 ^b
E	103.5±14.06	146.3±17.33 ^b	121.5±20.96 ^c	160.1±27.5 ^b	154.6±18.44 ^b
F	99.8±16.36	127.4±24.46 ^c	104.5±39.6 ^d	146.0±15.9 ^b	144.8±13.53 ^b

Values are Mean ± Standard Deviation for five animals per group. Different superscript in the same column are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. A: Normal Control; B: Diabetic Control; C: Diabetes + Standard Drug; D: Diabetes +5% Crude Oil, No Treatment; E: Diabetes + 5% Crude Oil + Standard Drug; F: Diabetes + 5% Crude Oil + Garlic + Standard Drug.

Table 2: Kidney function indices of control and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil.

Group	Urea (mg/dl)	Sodium (mmol/L)	Parameters			
			Potassium (mmol/L)	Creatinine (mEq/L)	Chloride (mg/dL)	Bicarbonate (mg/dL)
A	10.25±8.9 ^{bc}	632.25±74.77 ^{bc}	7.15±0.4 ^d	0.70±0.12 ^{ab}	29.00±2.31 ^a	75.00±23.09 ^b
B	8.55±4.62 ^c	498.1±106.46 ^{cd}	12.38±1.76 ^c	0.65±0.05 ^{ab}	30.75±7.22 ^a	90.00±14.24 ^{ab}
C	17.75±8.37 ^{bc}	1093.70±180.48 ^a	21.25±0.52 ^b	0.80±0.12 ^a	31.00±1.55 ^a	77.50±1.73 ^b
D	22.55±4.37 ^b	543.75±64.95 ^{bc}	15.40±5.31 ^c	0.55±0.06 ^c	18.75±0.50 ^b	76.25±12.42 ^b
E	87.35±3.18 ^a	662.00±71.59 ^b	34.95±2.02 ^a	0.75±0.06 ^{ab}	30.00±1.15 ^a	103.0±8.08 ^a
F	16.00±5.49 ^{bc}	359.8±73.3 ^d	14.58±2.16 ^c	0.78±0.23 ^a	20.40±2.88 ^b	97.40±21.47 ^{ab}

Values are mean standard Deviation for five animals per group. Different superscript in the same column are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$; A: Diabetic rats treated with standard drug, exposed to 5% crude oil; B: Diabetic rats treated with garlic extract and standard drug, exposed to crude oil; C: Diabetic rats treated with standard drug only; D: Diabetic control rats; E: Untreated diabetic rats exposed to crude Oil; F: Normal control rats.

I.a: Normal features of glomerulus and tubules

I.b: Normal kidney features

I.c: Slight tubular necrosis

1.d: Normal kidney features and adhesion

1.e: Tissue necrosis of the tubule

1.f: slight tubular necrosis

Plate 1: Histological examination of kidney of control and experimental animals treated with 200mg/kg body weight extract and 250mg/kg body weight metformin exposed to 5% crude oil for four weeks. Normal control group (1a); diabetic animals treated with garlic extract plus standard, exposed to 5% crude oil (1b); diabetic animals treated with standard drug exposed to 5% crude oil (1c); diabetic animals treated with standard drug (1d); diabetic control group(1e); diabetic animals exposed to 5% crude oil without treatment (1f). The red arrow indicates necrosis, yellow arrow indicates inflammation or congestion.

4.0 Discussion

During administration of *A. sativum* extract, there was no grossly negative behavior observed. There was however, a reduced reaction to noise, slow movement and resting at the corner of the cages. The reduced reaction to noise observed suggests the depressant effect of the extract on central nervous system. This is in line with study by [13]

In the present study, there was a significant drastic decrease in body weight of untreated diabetic rats compared with normal control rats. The decrease in weight of streptozocin induced diabetic rats compared to the normal control rats could be due to selective destruction of pancreatic beta cells of islet of Langerhans by streptozocin which caused hypoinsulinemia with a consequent decrease in peripheral uptake and utilization of glucose and increase in gluconeogenesis [14]. This caused increased degradation of structural proteins thereby affecting the body weight of the rats [9] [14]. During this study, the observed increase in weight found in diabetic rats treated with both the extract and standard drug after the first week of administration may be a function of anti-diabetic

effect of the drug and extract indicating synergistic effect. *Allium sativum* possess ability to reduce hyperglycemia and improve glucose metabolism which may lead to improve glucose uptake and utilization, decreased gluconeogenesis and increased glycogenesis which spares structural proteins from degradation thereby maintaining body weight [14]. Metformin was the drug of choice for the management of diabetes in the present study because of its effect of improved energy metabolism in cells preventing hepatic glucose production which inhibits gluconeogenesis in the liver [15] [16]. Besides, it was proven to have antioxidant, hypolipidaemic and insulin sensitizing effect which are known to reduce inflammation and oxidative stress caused as a result of streptozocin injection and crude oil exposure. *Allium sativum* extract was administered to rats receiving standard drug due to its established effect of inhibiting α -glucosidase enzyme, which reduces carbohydrate digestion, causing slow release of glucose into the blood, reducing hyperglycemia, in addition to its fiber content as well as the insulin secretion and insulin sensitizing effects [17]. It was also used due to its

hepato-protective effects to counter balance the effects of diabetes and crude oil exposure on liver and kidney where it was proven to improve kidney and hepatic functions, whilst metformin was contraindicated in animals with liver and kidney problems.

Human and animal exposures to crude oil and related hydrocarbons could induce toxic effects to various organs in the body, and is a public health concern due to increase release of toxic chemicals and wastes into the environment at hazardous levels [1][15]. In the present study, kidney functions of diabetic rats exposed to crude oil during treatment with metformin and garlic extract was evaluated. The result indicated significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in the level of plasma urea in diabetic rats treated with the extract and standard drug when compared to normal control, diabetic rats exposed to crude oil without treatment and diabetic control rats. It was also found that there was normal level of bicarbonate and electrolytes in all groups as was in control rats. The creatinine levels were almost the same in all groups.

Generally, renal tubular and glomerular cells may suffer considerable damage before losing sufficient function which manifest in the gross structure with modification in clinical parameters [3]. The increased level of urea found in diabetic rats exposed to crude oil without treatment suggest impairment in kidney function especially glomerulus in the process of urea extraction and urine formation [3]. It has been reported that about 50% or more of renal capacity can be lost before serum creatinine becomes abnormal and disease is detectable clinically [3]. Therefore, the normal levels of creatinine found in this study cannot adequately guaranty the safety of the rats' kidneys especially in the exposed rats.

Crude oil is reported to cause kidney abnormalities leading to kidney dysfunction in occupationally exposed young individuals [3]. The effect of changes in kidney function parameters is confirmed from the histological examination in which tubular necrosis, and tubular adhesion were found in diabetic rats treated with standard drug; diabetic rats exposed to crude oil treated with standard drug. There was slight tubular necrosis in rats treated with extract plus standard drug, exposed to crude oil. Creatinine levels of rats exposed to crude oil is therefore found to show no increase. This is in line with study by [3][15]. The values obtained for

creatinine seems not to conform the effects observed in the tissue plates. This may relatively be due to short duration of exposure to enable direct changes in the level of plasma creatinine and other kidney function markers.

The increase in serum creatinine, and potassium levels (though not significant $p > 0.05$) in the standard drug treated rats exposed to crude oil and the diabetic rats treated with standard drug compared with the control rats suggest renal pathology [4]. Also the significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in plasma urea, Na, bicarbonate and chloride of rats treated with the extract and standard drug compared to control suggests renal pathology. This agrees with study reported by [4].

The change in the gross structure of the renal cells might be due to generation of oxidative stress that caused activation of PKC raising the level of inflammatory markers. Generally inflammation play vital roles in progression of disease condition which progresses kidney dysfunction [14][15]. The changes in the cyto-architecture of renal cells observed in the exposed rats could be due to inflammation.

6.0 Conclusion

Crude oil exposure at 5% affects kidney functions of diabetic rats by inducing necrosis and inflammation of renal tubules despite treatment with metformin. This suggests that exposure to crude oil could cause kidney dysfunctions, thus interfering with diabetes management. Dietary intake of garlic would help improve and or maintain normal kidney functions of diabetic patients living in environments with crude oil exploration and refining.

6.0 Recommendation

Further studies are required to elucidate the molecular mechanism of nephrotoxicity of the crude oil exposure

7.0 Acknowledgement

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8.0 Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

9.0 References

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